

Australian Research Data Commons

Persistent Identifiers for ARDC Project Investments: Policy and Procedure

Date effective	19 June 2020
Review date	19 June 2021
Type	Policy and Procedure
Owner	Associate Director, Data & Services
Approved by	Director, Policy, Data & Services and Director, Platforms & Software
Category	Projects
Version Number	1.0
Audience	External
Content enquiries	contact@ardc.edu.au
Related documents	
Purpose	This policy states requirements for the use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) in ARDC investments

Requirements for PIDs in ARDC Investments

As specified in the [ARDC Persistent Identifiers Policy](#), the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) is critical because they provide identification of and connection between research objects and entities such as researchers, funders, organisations, articles, datasets, software, and samples. This enables better attribution and discovery of research and lays the foundation for better tracking of research impact. ARDC project investment also requires that data outputs be made FAIR. For these reasons it is a condition of ARDC investment that project outputs (data, software, platforms, publications) must have appropriate PIDs. Metadata describing those outputs should use persistent identifiers when referring to project activity and project inputs including funding, samples, instruments, facilities, people and organisations. Where exceptions are required, these should be documented with supporting rationale and ARDC approvals, in project documentation.

The ARDC’s suite of PID services, combined with those available through the AAF led Australian ORCID Consortium, form the backbone of enabling FAIR research outputs via PIDs in Australia. Through the ARDC’s [Data and Services](#) portfolio we provide [DOIs](#) (for research data, software, grey literature, instruments), [RAIDs](#) (for research projects), [IGSNs](#) (for physical objects collected during the course of research), [PURLs](#) (for research grants), and [Handles](#) (for data and for the foundation of RAIDs). PIDs are captured and displayed in [Research Data Australia](#) where international partners such as OpenAire harvest the information and display it in their own discovery portals, facilitating further exposure and impact of Australian research.

The two tables below provide ARDC investment partners with requirements as to which PIDs to use and how to get these PIDs. If you have questions or would like to discuss further, please contact services@ardc.edu.au

PIDs Implementation Table

Research objects and entities	PID(s) to use
Research datasets “published’ in a repository	DOI
Research software “published” in a repository	DOI
Research datasets or software not yet published	Handle
Conference papers and “grey literature” related to the project “published” in a repository	DOI
Research instruments	DOI (preferred) or Handle
Platforms	DOI
Research organisations	ROR
Researchers and other people associated with the	ORCID

project	
Physical samples	IGSN
Research grants from ARC and NHMRC	PURL
ARDC project investment	DOI
Project activities	RAID

How to get PIDs

PID to use	How to get PIDs
DOI	Options include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use ARDC DOI service offered in partnership with DataCite Use another DOI service
Handle	Options include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use the ARDC Handle Service Use another Handle service
ROR	Use the Research Organization Registry
ORCID	Options include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use ORCID directly Use ORCID via an ORCID member institution (contact the Australian ORCID Consortium if needed)
IGSN	Options include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use the ARDC IGSN Service Use another IGSN Allocating Agent
PURL	Assigned by ARDC and displayed in Research Data Australia grants portal
DOI for ARDC Investments	ARDC will assign this at the start of every project. The DOI will be issued by ARDC through CrossRef DOI Registration Agency. ARDC will advise the partner of the DOI issued. Partners should also refer to For ARDC Partners: How to attribute ARDC Project Investment
RAID for ARDC Investments	ARDC will assign this at the start of every project and advise the partner of the RAID issued. It is then the responsibility of the Partner to ensure that the RAID manifest is updated with other PIDs related to the project.